

Mushrooms can save the world

EU HORIZON 2020 VegWaMus CirCrop - zero-waste policymaking project by closing the loop between food waste based biogas production and mushroom and vegetable cultivation

VegWaMus CirCrop (VWMCC) is a Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie Individual Fellowship project, where Dr Agnieszka Jasinska is developing commercial mushroom and vegetable production in an integrated food to waste to food biosystem. Mushroom and plant crop cultivation are usually performed through energy and resource-intensive processes (based on fossil or mineral resources), which generate waste and a high CO₂ footprint. The main focus has been on plant crops, but integrated mushroom cultivation has been found to be highly interesting from both a circular, approach in which organic wastes are utilised for both energy (renewable biogas), and crop production in a closed system.

It was coincidence that Dr Jasinska began to study and experiment on mushrooms, but soon she was hooked on those small and big miracle workers.

“One of the most fascinating things about mushrooms is that they can break down virtually anything and build something new,” says Dr Jasinska. “Mushrooms have ‘magical’ properties for breaking down materials considered as wastes by others, such as straw, wood chips, corn cobs, coffee grains—basically anything organic. In nature, mushrooms play an enormous role as decomposers, without which the world would draw in organic litter in no time. It is exciting to research new uses for mushrooms, other than just being food. Everybody knows about mycorrhiza, the special symbiosis between higher plants

such as trees and basidiomycete mushrooms such as King Boletus, however it is not as obvious that 80% of all plants on Earth live in symbiosis with fungi, and that without fungi there would be almost no life on Earth. We know that some mushrooms are edible and contain important proteins and vitamins, some are poisonous and others can cure disease. In Asia, over 150 different species of fungi are cultivated, and they are widely used in medicine.”

In the VegWaMus CirCrop project mushrooms are grown at a commercial level on food waste digestate (Stoknes et al., 2013), mushroom compost is produced using renewable energy, the growth itself releases CO₂ to the greenhouse atmosphere, and the spent mushroom substrate is mixed into plant growing substrates promoting increased plant crop yields and suppression of plant diseases. Thus, mushroom cultivation can be highly sustainable and commercially viable.

Figure 1. VegWaMus CirCrop closed loop system

Figure 2. Mushrooms can save the World – Food to Waste to Food biosystem

As the mushroom production is based on agricultural, horticultural and forestry waste—which are used as cultivation substrate—it meets up with waste management policies, helping to utilise many troublesome wastes. In the same time transferring that waste to high quality

nourishing food, even gourmet foods, mushroom production fits perfectly in the sustainability policies. **Mushrooms become increasingly attractive as functional foods for nutritional, medicinal effects, vitamin D booster as well as a source of cosmetic and nutricosmetics.**

Figure 3. Food to Waste to Food project

Recently much attention has been placed on so-called urban farming, since shrinking land capacity requires novel solutions such as vertical cultivation and crop production or circular crop production (combined cultivation of mushrooms and plants, plants and fishes etc.). Those kinds of actions are mostly undertaken for small or non-commercial scale. In the

scope of the presented project, the main action is the development of commercially stable, sustainable products, i.e. healthy vegetables and mushrooms, based on renewable resources of food-waste (FW), green waste (GW), spent mushroom substrate (SMS) and anaerobically digestion biogas by-product (DIG).

In the EU project Food to Waste to Food, we cultivated different species of mushrooms on the bee residue that remained after biogas production.

1. We can use the fibres left after the biogas process to produce new food directly. The mushroom breaks down the fibres and creates a new, useful crop.
2. We can utilise the areas of the greenhouse twice. Mushrooms under, plants over. Mushrooms also release CO₂, fertilising the greenhouse air so that the plants grow better.
3. The used mushroom substrate is an excellent growth medium for the plants. The pH decreases as the fungus grows in the biorest. Plants like that. Thus, we can reduce peat use (peat use emits fossil CO₂).

Biogas produced from organic waste is considered a green energy, but production strongly depended on raw materials and operation practices. Recently a sustainable approach has been observed; biogas plants operated on pure food waste, which is highly biodegradable and increases methane production. It is estimated that yearly, one third (approximately 1.3 billion tons) of the food produced globally for human consumption gets lost or wasted (FAO 2011).

Within the VWMCC food waste treated in anaerobic digestion (AD) is considered as a multicomponent organic fertiliser and by-product for plant and mushroom cultivation substrate. Sustainable horticulture should reuse organic waste. The objectives of project are achieved by indicating mushroom species which grow commercially on substrate based on digestate, and vegetable plants grown reusing spent mushroom compost (substrate after cultivation). Combined cultivation will be incorporated in a sustainable greenhouse environment in the food to waste to food biosystem based on crop and substrate circulation. Lindum AS, a Norwegian company and leader in waste treatment, and associated partners have for several years developed a more circular approach in which organic wastes are utilised for both energy (renewable biogas) and crop production in a closed system.

